

Primary school teachers' views regarding the school's response to the challenge of children with chronic diseases in a regular classroom: A qualitative approach

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Abstract

Many children with chronic diseases attend public school in regular classrooms and have to manage not only the educational demands, but also the demands of the disease. At the same time, their teachers have the responsibility of both educating and managing them in school, keeping them safe, providing equal opportunities for learning, and generally optimizing the school experience for these children. The question of whether the school is meeting this challenge is therefore of vital importance for these children whatever their needs in the school setting in general and in the classroom in particular. This research forms part of a PhD thesis, which examines the issue of children's chronic conditions in mainstream school and mainstream classrooms, the school experience of children, parents and teachers as affected by a chronic condition, and the role that counselling can play.

Key words: Chronic conditions, teachers, school response

1. Introduction

One of the most important problems facing modern societies is the problem of chronic diseases. According to the definition provided by the World Health Organization (WHO), chronic diseases are long-lasting and slowly progressive, while other agencies, such as the National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention in America, as well as the American Academy of Pediatrics include chronic diseases and diseases which are contagious, such as HIV-AIDS. By mid-1990s, half of the world's deaths were due to chronic diseases (WHO, 1995) and the rates are constantly increasing dramatically (Walters, 2015), while by 2025 half of Europe's population will suffer from allergies (EAACI, 2013). A significant proportion of these chronic patients are school-aged children and adolescents, who are still attending regular schools, so several questions are raised about the issue. For example, whether the school responds to this challenge, how and to what extent, what is the role of the stakeholders and parents, etc.

The responsiveness of a system depends to a very large extent on the individual units of that system. When it comes to systems that require clear and strict structures to function, like the education system, the role of the teacher - as the most basic part of the system - is critical. Schools must be able to identify, include and have the means available to manage each case individually. The burden, of course, rests on the shoulders of front-line educators, according to whom there are still many gaps in this matter. According to them, although the school is improving, the road to including the special needs of children with chronic conditions is still long.

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2. Methodology

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with primary school teachers, following the principles of qualitative research. This method allows for an in-depth investigation and understanding of a topic and especially topics that have not been widely explored and, therefore, are approached exploratorily. The purpose was to investigate the school experience of the teachers, regarding the school's response to the issue of children's chronic diseases in the mainstream public primary school.

2.1 Sample

The sample consisted of sixteen active primary school teachers, who teach in a regular class and with different years of experience. All teachers had contact with a child with a chronic illness in their class, more than once. Sampling was done using the avalanche method, a method which is considered ideal when the sample is difficult to access and the subject is particularly sensitive (Parker, Scott & Geddes, 2019). The sample data are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Sample Data

Code	Name	Years of service	Child with chronic disease in class	Chronic disease	First aid training
PA1	Dimitris	35	Yes	Diabetes T1, Mental illness, Autism	Yes
PA2	Zoe	32	Yes	Diabetes, Epilepsy, Autoimmune, ADHD, Mental illness	Yes
PA3	Amalia	27	Yes	Cancer, ADHD, Epilepsy, Diabetes, Haemophilia	Yes
PA4	Elena	22	Yes	Diabetes T1, Cancer	No
PA5	Fotini	22	Yes	Diabetes T1, ADHD, Autoimmune	No
PA6	Elina	22	Yes	Epilepsy, Diabetes, ADHD	Yes
PA7	Nikoleta	21	Yes	ADHD, Diabetes T1, Asthma, Epilepsy	Yes
PA8	George	21	Yes	Diabetes T1, ADHD	Yes
PA9	Maria	21	Yes	Hearing, Autism, ADHD	No
PA10	Eftychia	20	Yes	Diabetes T1, ADHD, Asperger	No

PA11	Xenia	20	Yes	ADHD, Diabetes T1, Epilepsy	No
PA12	Eva	18	Yes	Asthma, Epilepsy, ADHD	No
PA13	Rena	17	Yes	Diabetes T1	No
PA14	Markos	16	Yes	Diabetes T1	No
PA15	Haroulla	13	Yes	Diabetes T1, Partial blindness, Quadriplegic, Asthma	No
PA16	Kyriakos	11	Yes	Hemiplegia, Food allergy (Anaphylaxis), ADHD	No

2. 2. Data collection and analysis

The data was collected through semi-structured interviews, at a time and place chosen by the participants, since the semi-structured interview provides the opportunity to express personal opinions and develop discussions around the topic of interest. Each interview was audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim so that tone and style were preserved, and each interview was accompanied by researcher field notes. Data collection was stopped when saturation was reached and it became clear that no new evidence would emerge (Patton, 2002; Latham, 2013). Finally, the data processing was carried out based on the thematic analysis of Braun and Clarke (2006), a very influential framework to date, as it is clear and practical.

3. Results

Regarding the school's response to the challenge of the chronic illnesses of the children-students, the teachers expressed opinions on four main issues. Specifically, what do they themselves consider to be their capabilities - and by extension the school's - to respond to the special needs of these children, based on their knowledge, the readiness of some teachers versus others, the dissemination of information within the school unit and in issues of discrimination against children with chronic diseases. These four issues outline the school's response to the challenge of children's chronic illnesses, through the eyes of the participants.

3.1. Teacher knowledge: *The view from the inside*

Participating teachers refer extensively to the issue of the school's ability to currently respond to the challenge of chronic illness, developing various sub-themes. The opinions of the participants can be summed up in Haroulla's opinion which, after thinking, includes in one sentence some basic keywords, which seem to convey the general picture: *it does not respond adequately*. This statement is fully supported by what other participants have to say, who focus on various elements to explain their view that there is still much to be done. Zoe, a teacher with many years of experience, refers to many gaps, which according to her own experience the school does not respond and refers to these gaps with intensity: *“Psychologically, structurally, systematically, with additional hours in the program and with teachers or other people, no! (the school does not respond). There are many gaps. Lots of gaps”* (Zoe).

The most important gap is identified by the participants in the lack of knowledge about chronic illnesses, a lack which makes their work difficult and determines the school's ability to respond as a microsystem. Amalia, for example, explains that responsiveness is an issue that requires more than good intentions from teachers and principals: *"Surely the school cannot cope even though there are good intentions from both teachers and principals. [...] I can't say that we have the knowledge, the means, the support to help"* (Amalia).

Markos and Maria tried to give a more optimistic note, without however managing to delete a 'but', which seems to be imposed on any positive thought. Markos states that the school is responding, but: *"There is always room for improvement and there are always problems that act as a brake on these efforts. Many times, it can be the lack of cooperation with the parent, it can be the excessively difficult case, a student, the lack of knowledge..."* (Markos). For the very positive teachers who participated, it seems that the school is responding to a degree, certainly not to the extent required, since in this challenge - as in others that require more specialized management - the teacher without specialized knowledge is the one who is called upon to bear the brunt.

In fact, there are many incidents in schools and according to the majority of the participants, the teacher himself is not ready to cope and therefore neither is the school itself: *"Incidents exist in schools. Many in fact. [...] But the school is not prepared. Because the teacher is not prepared, he does not have the knowledge to do it"* (Eva). In fact, whether the teacher is prepared for this challenge concerns other participants as well, and each of them attributes this readiness to their own reasons.

Therefore, it is up to the discretion of the school staff themselves, whether it is the principal or the class teacher: *"It depends on each school, the principal, the teachers... There is not something that applies to all schools, to generalize. But he does not have the necessary support (the teacher). Not to the extent that the teacher should have, and he cannot cope. We don't even have the knowledge to understand these issues"* (Xenia).

Eftychia explains that an additional issue that is directly related to the ability of the teacher to cope - and by extension the ability of the school to respond - concerns the very experience with the various chronic illnesses and the knowledge that the teacher may acquire with experience. In cases where experience is not accumulated, as she states, the teacher is ignorant: *"Of course the school does not respond, especially - as you understand - about cases that you haven't seen before [...] Cases that have not happened to me and I have not spoken to psychologists or with specialists, nor with doctors, I am completely ignorant"* (Eftychia).

Because of the lack of knowledge about chronic conditions, responding to the challenge to any extent is directly dependent on the teacher's and the principal's good will: *"The school can only respond to a point. If the problem is not serious, I think yes it can. But again, this depends on the good will of both the teacher and the principal"* (Elena). Thus, we could say that the situation is rather fluid and to a certain extent the school cannot respond without personal initiatives and the good will of front-line teachers and some who may have some additional knowledge: *"I think at discretion of the management and of the teachers and of the 'exploitation' of a teacher who may have more knowledge. Either by chance or because he has it in his family or because he has some special interest. Only like that. Like me, I have a colleague who has a doctorate in diabetes, we will take advantage of it, but this is not common"* (Rena).

It seems that it is very difficult for the teacher to manage, to the extent required, the cases of chronic illnesses in the school, let alone when he must deal with something really serious. Indeed, George and Eva explain that the teacher has significant deficiencies in terms of knowledge, therefore he can only intervene where things do not require special knowledge or skills: *"We are not ready. Not even trained. Not at all. I only consider some incidents that, in the simplest terms, we can manage. Common things"* (Eva). Therefore, as George adds, the teacher feels that he can cope as long as nothing serious happens: *"As long as nothing serious happens, yes, the teacher can cope. When something serious happens, no."*

I speak as simply as I can. I had a diabetic student with the machine on him. If by chance the child needed help, I don't know if I could really help him, besides calling someone. There is a weakness, it is not easy. In other words, if something serious happens, the school may not be able to respond” (George). Concluding his thought, he expresses the complaint that the teacher is in a difficult position, since he is in a place with children, many hours during the day, with the only real action he can take in a crisis is to pick up the phone and notify someone: *“Beyond notifying someone, an ambulance, the parent, anyone, what can you do? [...] You are in a place with a child for so many hours. You must be prepared for anything that happens, be knowledgeable, not just for alerting someone in case of need. We became messengers, we just notify along”* (George).

Zoe, after 32 years of experience, concludes that: *“There is a problem of structures and there is a problem of lack of policy and vision”* (Zoe). The issue of politics and structures engaged both Dimitris and Zoe, as well as George, during their interviews, who commented on what they consider to be an important gap in the system. Dimitris, in fact, considers it a flagrant violation of children's rights: *“There is no fixed policy, strategy to say the least, to have structures and procedures to help and respect the child's right to be served to the maximum extent without risk to his health. It's a reality”* (Dimitris). On the same issue, Georges' caustic remarks are disarming: *“Knowledge? What knowledge? It reminds me of a conversation with someone who said, 'we dream of Finnish systems but with Cypriot funds'. The most economical model of a Finnish system. It's not possible. Now the inspector comes in and checks if I have my 'Won't Forget' sign on the board or if I put a comma where I should. Well done - comma - Sotirakis, for example. And they will care for the diseases?”* (George).

3.2. The indifference factor: Educational patriotism²

Another issue that concerns the teachers who participated is the attitude of the teacher himself. Previously, some teachers referred to the good will and the teacher's effort to rise to the challenge, since there are many gaps in the system in terms of procedures. During the interviews, information was requested about the general attitude of the teacher towards these issues, to explore the issue more deeply. The participants themselves report that there are individuals in the group who act with indifference or are strictly and exclusively limited to their teaching duties.

First of all, the participants' reports are of particular importance to the fact that since the required knowledge or specific mechanism does not exist, any response, action and reaction is up to the teacher himself and his personality. Haroulla, an educator with clearly a positive attitude, refers to the sensitivity and conscientiousness of the teacher and believes that there are many teachers with these elements: *“It depends on the sensitivity of the teacher, how good he will be informed. That is, thank God, we have many conscientious teachers. But surely there are also.... Some may not be so sensitive about some issues. So... the child who has a problem is at the mercy of his teacher's magnanimity and his sensitivity”* (Haroulla).

So, what is required for the teacher to show "mercy" and "sensitivity"? For Markos, the attitude of the individual towards his profession is decisive, his passion and will are what define his work, as in any profession: *“Look, for me always, always, the attitude of the individual is decisive. Whether it concerns an educator or any other professional. That is, your passion, your will for progressiveness, for improving knowledge, for improving your wider social group, which is also a class, let's say, a school. Anyway, I think that the teacher's need to provide, to help, to educate himself is very important. And his attitude towards these cases”* (Markos).

²The word is used in a purely metaphorical sense. It was adopted after a report by two teachers who wanted to declare their passion for their profession in this way.

Obviously, a lot depends on the personality and character of the teacher. George adds that the primary school teacher is inevitably closer to the children and has the time required to devote to each case. But it is up to the teacher himself whether he will do it: *"The teacher has time. In primary school, I feel we are closer to the children. We have more hours with the children and can attend to a child when needed. But we have such a heavy workload. Therefore, it is up to each teacher. We have time, a lot of time. But we must have the willingness"* (George).

The fact that the school level plays an important role in the teacher's attitude and sensitivity was also mentioned by other teachers. Amalia, who takes a more moderate stance in her positions, avoids the word indifference, and uses the phrase 'less willing', perhaps with a hint of guilt or a need to defend herself: *"We are not indifferent. I can say that I did not particularly experience the issue of indifference. It happened that colleagues, at least with whom I worked, some were less willing and others more..."* (Amalia).

For Fotini, those who are less willing are fortunately few: *"I think the percentage of us in primary education who do this (showing sensitivity) is high. And I'm glad to say this. Because I saw that we have very responsible teachers and I think we still have the sensitivities [...] As school units we are smaller, but you are also in direct contact with the children. I think the percentage that doesn't do it is minimal. I think there is still a lot of sensitivity. If it didn't exist, there would be many problems in these matters"* (Fotini).

Zoe believes that either there are many or few in not important, since the bottom line is that there are always those who are willing to help and teachers in Cyprus are aware and sensitive: *"Teachers in Cyprus are aware and sensitive. Besides, in a school there may be some who do not want or are not willing but there are always those five who are willing to help. There will always be people willing to help or take action"* (Zoe). Considering the teachers themselves, their response and, by extension, the school's, is ultimately a question of *"initiative and interest and excessive zeal..."* (Dimitris).

Indeed, this group of "not so willing" teachers does exist. How do the participants themselves describe this group? Elena refers to this group as the group that always complains that it is not their duty to manage these children: *"There are some people who... Keep moaning around: 'But it is not my duty to have this'"* (Elena). The issue of duties seems to be an important factor for such attitudes: *"Many people tell you, okay, my work is at school, I don't care about home. But you must enter every child's house at some point. That is, every child...experiences something. It depends on the good will of the teacher. Unfortunately, many act strictly professionally, they say 'it's not my responsibility' etc., but in fact it is!"* (George).

Things seem to sometimes take a more "dangerous" turn since some teachers not only do they consider teaching to be their only task, but their attitude towards children with chronic diseases reaches the limits of rejection, since they consider that they should be outside the specific context and possibly in a different kind of school: *"[...] their attitude is 'I go to school and I finish my job and leave me alone, I have no other responsibility. I'm here only for the teaching part, I'm ready to do my class, but you're bothering me about something else' and they don't even accept these children who are ill. Their own teachers. They believe that this is something else, let's say, that these children are for a different context. Outside of school I mean. Out of school and in a (special) unit"* (Maria). So, it is a somewhat fluid situation, as Zoe puts it: *"It's... how can I tell you... things are a bit fluid like that. You do it only if you want to do it. There are colleagues who say no, this is not our job, it is the job of the school medical service, I do not touch this topic"* (Zoe).

It is expected, as in any social context, that there are various and different groups of people at school. For two participants, what causes a negative impression is the direct or indirect attempt of other teachers to limit their action, when they try to offer more to the children with chronic diseases in the classroom, because they consider that such a thing is outside from the duties of a teacher. Although such

phenomena were not mentioned by other participants, it is nevertheless considered necessary to mention them for a more complete picture.

Eftychia reports that some colleagues, with their comments, sometimes try to discourage her or put pressure on her as to which subjects are a priority and which are not: *“From other teachers you may get different things. They even terrorize you. I mean... sometimes... you know... Some comments discourage you. I would have prioritized this part, let's say, but then they come to you about other issues, pressing you and telling you that you are not ok with your other duties”* (Eftychia). Eva agrees that this group of teachers does exist, and sometimes forces her to limit her actions too, in order not to have problems with her colleagues: *“There is a group that shouts these things at you for your duties, so you have to act differently. You may have 'patriotism' because you want to feel... your personality, your character has it, to feel that you want to give something more, and this behavior of them can really hold you back sometimes, in order to have balance with your colleagues. I don't know if I was clear”* (Eva).

Of course, as Elina mentions, any negative attitude of any teacher should not be considered unrelated to his experiences and especially any negative experiences he has, but also to his fears about something for which he can get into serious trouble: *“Okay, sometimes it's just indifference. I'm sorry to say it, but this is everywhere, not just in the education system. There is a percentage of colleagues who are indifferent to this, that is, “I don't want to deal with such a thing”. Either because I'm afraid that I'd be exposed if I get involved, or because I've had negative experiences and now, let's say, I'm holding back”* (Elina).

Nicoleta places herself somewhere in the middle, presenting a more moderate teacher. Showing understanding for those colleagues who are concerned only with the teaching part, she explains that there are issues that are indeed outside the duties of the profession, while there are other factors that determine the specific attitude towards the subject: *“I understand the people who say, ‘I'll do my job and go home’. Just to get ahead of you, not to become a hero for no reason, I don't put myself in the category of the teachers that do everything, who sacrifice themselves, I am not that. I'm somewhere in between. There are things outside the teacher's profession and there are other factors that play their role”* (Nicoleta).

Indeed, these other factors seem to exist, and the participants refer to them in their interviews. For example, reference is made to the constraints placed on the teacher from outside, the attitudes of parents and the society, and the motivations the teacher need in order to go beyond his strict duties in a school unit or to seek additional knowledge and training.

One such important issue concerns the treatment of the teacher by parents and society. Indeed, for some participants, the attitude of parents and the wider society also plays an important role in any attitude that translates as indifference on the part of teachers. This attitude, according to Rena, reaches the limits of aggression: *“There is enmity from the parents... from the media too... [...] That is, this disrespect, that everything that happens is the teachers' fault. This really plays a role... If you know that everyone is ready to scold you for the slightest thing, to exaggerate it many times, to take it further - yes, we live in a small society- or if it has a very serious impact, for example to face charges, it is unlikely to take it on”* (Rena).

It seems, therefore, that the attitude of the parents and the public influence the attitude of the teacher himself. In this regard, the testimony of Nicoletta is important, since in the past she agreed to administer medicine at school, something she is now not sure if she would do, explaining that the teacher is not indifferent, but scared: *“No, not indifferent. I think he's scared. This category doesn't want to take responsibility, because if something goes wrong it won't go unpunished. They are not the type of people that say, ‘I don't care, cut off your head’. I justify them. In fact, as the years go by and I experience more and more things, such as the anger of parents against teachers, now I'm not sure that I would have done it. I might not. Because if I made a mistake ten years ago, the parents could have said okay,*

at least the teacher tried to help. Now you are not going to get away with it, if you make a mistake, you pay dearly for it. You will pay for it in gold” (Nicoleta).

For Maria, everything is a matter of culture, for which the state itself bears responsibility, as precisely because of this lack of culture neither acceptance is cultivated nor the teacher seeks to improve in skills and knowledge: *“It’s a matter of culture, it’s a matter of the state that we didn’t cultivate a culture of acceptance of these children. Many, after their studies, let’s say, I’m talking about primary school teachers, from then on nobody invested in learning anything else. Nobody invests their time. In the Gymnasium and High School, things might be worse, because everyone deals with their own subject of interest” (Maria).*

Xenia and Kyriakos also mention the issue of incentives, an issue that has been discussed a lot in recent years at the administrative level, for all levels of education. In Xenia's opinion, the majority of teachers show interest and build relationships with the children, but through an evaluation system, the corresponding incentives must be given, and their work should be recognized: *“[...] But in many ways... I consider that somehow there should be a proper evaluation system, so that the teachers would have more incentives to work. To have personal motivation, to be able to feel that their time and effort are valued. Since there are some people who don't care, those who are different should feel that there is something more for them. Now the system is flat, I think it's the same for everyone. So, this is disincentive for some” (Xenia).*

Kyriakos explains that these incentives can take the form of exemptions or facilitations, since the teacher is asked to do things beyond his duties or the educational time allocated to him: *“It is in the patriotism of the teacher, of the teacher to go and look for more... But everyone who has their own family, who finishes work and goes home and must go open books, must go ask experts, go to... And no expert would support you for free. [...] The teacher has a thousand things too and has kids to take in after school activities. I understand them (those who don't want to do more). In the back of their minds, they get into other hustles and bustles, so they say ‘oops, what do I get?’ [...] Think of a teacher, you will send him to train to be a first aider, you’ll send him here and there, he can’t be torn into a thousand pieces, what kind of teacher will he be? Will he get paid more to do his chores? Do you understand;” (Kyriakos). For George, however, things are much clearer about what the teacher's duties are: *“What is my job? In other words, teaching is not only the class, it’s caring too. Otherwise, what kind of teacher are you? You don’t just teach” (George).**

3.3. The diffusion of information: The cut water lily

Considering that, in some way, the information often reaches the school, it is worth asking what happens to it, how it spreads and to what depth. Although one would expect that in school, the dissemination of information either in the pedagogical groups or in the staff session would be a given, according to the participants, things are not so clear. Elena explains the process in the staff session: *“What we do: in the staff session, the class teacher is informed as well as the others and the visiting teachers too, everyone who enters the class, but also for the break time too, so we know what's going on. Basically, if a child has diabetes and I see him during the break and he is not well, I must know how to react. That's how it happens” (Elena).*

Markos agrees that in similar cases these issues are mentioned in the staff session, so that the teachers are informed, especially for the time when the students are having a break outside: *“There is information in such cases. Because other teachers also socialize with the child and all schoolteachers must know. Not just the teacher who is present in the area where the child is playing... All the teachers of the school must be aware of the problem. Mainly for this reason. For the reason of pedonomy” (Markos).*

Fotini states that in such sessions important information is exchanged and management instructions are given, so that the teacher knows what to do in case of an emergency: *“If, so to speak, an incident*

occurs, there is a briefing in a staff session and we have some instructions from the parents which they received from the doctor, to share with us, to -theoretically- know what to do if something bad happens” (Fotini). This, George explains, is a constant process and is always activated and all the teachers are informed without exception: *“It never happened to me a child to have something serious and not be informed. At the beginning of each school year, we have a list of children we must pay attention to. Which is confidential. We sit down... Class E1 e.g. has such and such a child, class E2 has such and such a child, so that we and the visiting teachers are informed in general”* (George).

On the other hand, Kyriakos explains that this procedure is usually done for the class teacher and not for everyone, and only when there are serious cases and more so when these cases can in some way affect school life. However, it is all coming to sharing the information plainly and not clear instructions as previously mentioned by Fotini: *“It is supposed that if you take a class, you must know the background of the children [...] We say some things in pedagogical meetings. Very simple, just mentions”* (Kyriakos). Rena makes the same reference: *“The visitors teachers knew, as well as the others. The update was made by the management. It was just a report and an instruction for me to have this or that in my drawer. In case the teacher in my class needs to give something to the child”* (Rena).

Eftychia also spoke about the pedagogical meetings, explaining that the information is given only in cases where the child receives medication, and it is just plain information, no details. In such cases and under normal circumstances, the parent comes to administer the medicine, and the teacher is only aware of the matter: *“Okay, the only thing that is clear to the groups, who inform us regularly of is if there is a child taking medication. And normally the parent comes to give it to him. This is the clear part. Just for us to know”* (Eftychia).

Maria, in her 21 years of career, never received detailed and clear information about any of the cases she faced: *“In the pedagogical meetings, yes, we will discuss it. Not extensively, don’t think of anything special here, we will just mention some things. Purely informative. Nothing special. Simply that the child has this problem. With details etc.? Never”* (Maria).

Xenia mentions another important issue regarding information in pedagogical meetings, which concerns feedback. As she explains, pedagogical meetings are convened and information is shared, but apart from the fact that nothing substantial is done, there is no feedback over time. In fact, more information is exchanged during the breaks, in the form of small talk between colleagues: *“There is no feedback as it should be, that is, to come back to it again in two months or three months, bring back the incidents, etc., add information. Most information is shared during our breaks where you can talk with your colleague, but nothing official”* (Elina).

She also mentions that in many cases she did not receive any important information, giving as an example a case of diabetes, which she has this year at school, stating that these updates are not always carried out: *“A lot is done but not always I would say. I have several cases where the information was vertical (not to all teachers). Not on purpose, you know what I mean, but there was a lack of information. This year I have a little girl with diabetes. [...] I’m still missing basic information”* (Elina).

There are also teachers who report that this process is not taking place at all, even though they had children with chronic conditions in their class. Amalia, in her 27 years of career in schools, states that she has never been informed of such cases in the context of pedagogical meetings: *“In pedagogical meetings, no. I was not informed about such cases”* (Amalia), a statement supported by Xenia: *“It never happened to do this procedure in the pedagogical meetings”* (Xenia).

Finally, a report that gives us an insight into the reasoning of a particularly experienced teacher, is Zoe's report on issues of regulations on personal data and the dissemination of information. She herself, despite knowing the regulations, chose to inform the other teachers during the staff session, following what she calls her own spirit of the law: *“Although it is forbidden to discuss children's personal data in the staff session, I was forced to speak to staff session for specific children, thus violating the regulation, because these children could suffer from anything during break time or when another*

colleague was in the classroom. Therefore, it's not only the class teacher who should have knowledge. So, I felt I had to inform everybody [...] But doing so I was not covered by the law. I was covered by my own spirit of the law, as I personally interpreted it" (Zoe).

3.4. Distinctions: One size fits all

According to the participants, the school shows a weakness in responding to the special needs of children with chronic diseases and they support their opinions with various facts, which have been mentioned above. The question that inevitably arises is what the impact of this weakness on the children is and on the others involved. Because when the core of education, the front-line educator faces these kinds of problems, surely the children themselves are not unaffected. Indeed, some teachers report issues that should cause some serious concern.

Eftychia, a teacher with great sensitivity, explains that she is very disturbed when these children are stigmatized at school and unfortunately, they are also stigmatized by teachers, unwittingly: *"Unfortunately, the system does not support these children enough, not only when it comes to chronic diseases, but for psychological or other issues. It's not very supportive. For me, what worries me and that's why I pay more attention is... I don't like children being labeled. At all. And unfortunately, it happens, unintentionally but it happens" (Eftychia).*

In fact, Elina mentions the case of a child with autistic characteristics in a regular class, and due to the school's inability to cope, the child ended up in another school, in a special class. She and the teacher responsible of the child consider this decision wrong: *"E.g. this case that I told you about, this child, in the end it ended up in a special class, that is, in a school that had a special class. For me and my colleague this was not the right choice. Because this child didn't belong there. I mean he wanted attention and care yes, but that doesn't mean he had to go into a special class that had other children with other symptoms that... you get the idea. It was unfair for the child" (Elina).*

Other children, who face difficulties or suffer from some syndrome for which a diagnosis has not yet been made, go unnoticed, with all that entails: *"I think that in general there are children with difficulties who go unnoticed. They are not getting the support they should get from the system in general. There is no detection, no diagnosis, no special support. Because there are children who may have autism characteristics for example. But for someone to be able to manage them, to manage the behavior of some children... So, I think there are cases where there was no detection or correct diagnosis. Because these children don't get the right help" (Xenia).* In addition, children with special conditions such as chronic diseases, according to Maria, experience social isolation in schools if they do not receive proper care and the attention required: *"So many children experience social isolation. It happened to me to see it and to go to him and talk to him. He was socially isolated; he had no friends" (Maria).*

In a regular classroom, the teacher needs training and knowledge to be able to understand and above all to deal with these cases seriously: *"In a general classroom, I see that the teachers are not ready. They need a lot of preparation, they need training, they need support from experts, in order to be able to understand the problem and the seriousness of the problem. Educators focus too much on children's educational deficits instead of their emotions. [...] These matters should be taken more seriously as chronic illnesses or anything that torments a child is not just something you should take lightly. It's something where you should show empathy for this child. Because we say we provide equal learning opportunities, equal opportunities in education, etc. etc. But in reality, we are not. It takes a lot of empathy to put yourself in the position of the child, let's say, how he might feel, not to exclude it" (Maria).*

Rena, refers to how the classmates of a child with diabetes were informed, not realizing that the whole process may have embarrassed the child, made him an 'focus of attention' and exposed him to

the eyes of other children. In fact, the information was given on the initiative of the principal and not with the instructions of an expert: *“It was 4th grade. Okay, it surprised them (the classmates) the first few days. We informed the children, because we thought that they might don't want to see the procedure (of taking medication) etc. Okay, they just commented on the... that he'll be like this or... or he'll do that. OK, after that they didn't pay much attention.”* (Rena).

According to Nicoleta, the school is ‘one size fits all’ and definitely needs something more specialized for these children, something that currently depends solely on the teacher: *“School is a bit of a one size fits all style, that's okay students want something more specialized. Now it is up to the teacher. I mean, if the teacher does it on his own because he wants to, because he is worried, because he is stressed, because something can be done, but in general the educational system, I think no, is not responding”* (Nicoleta). For the time being, the situation may seem under control, but we can't help but wonder if it's really under control, or just under control until it's proven that it's not.

4. Discussion - Conclusions

Regarding the overall response of the school, the inside picture as presented by the participants indicates that the school does not adequately respond to any needs of the children with chronic conditions, mainly due to the limited ability of teachers to meet the challenge, not always on their fault. No teacher explicitly states that the school responds to the desired level, while those of them who state that there is a certain response, explain that it only occurs to a certain extent or as long as nothing serious happens.

An important issue of concern is the teachers' knowledge about chronic diseases, for which the participants agree that it is incomplete and with serious gaps. Although the quality of teachers' knowledge about chronic diseases has beneficial effects on the quality of life of children and their families (Helms et al., 2016; Janin et al., 2018), research indicates that reality is far from ideal. The specific issue is examined in the literature both from the point of view of the teachers themselves and from the point of view of the parents, putting under the microscope not only the degree but also the quality of the existing knowledge.

For example, Kambra and her colleagues (2016), in a survey conducted in Greece on the knowledge of teachers about epilepsy, report that although there has been progress over time, there is still significant room for improvement. In addition, they indicate the need for better information and training of teachers for emergencies at school. Other studies make similar recommendations. Berger and colleagues (2018), indicate that teachers need training and support in the management of chronic conditions, confirming findings of other research, past and recent (e.g. Abulhamail et al., 2014; Driskoll et al., 2015; Nguyen, Pertini & Kettler, 2015; Brabcova, Kohout & Krsek, 2016; Kise, Hopkins & Burke, 2017; Yilmazel & Cetinkaya, 2017; Urrutia-Pereira et al., 2018; Jones et al., 2018). As for Cyprus, a recent survey by Stavrou and Dimitriou (2019), in which a questionnaire based on the Perception Scale for People with Epilepsy was administered, showed both a lack of knowledge about epilepsy and serious misconceptions about it in public school.

Teachers' lack of knowledge is not limited to epilepsy, but the problem extends across the spectrum of chronic conditions. For example, Kofidou et al. (2017), have conducted a literature review which indicates that the majority of teachers have little or insufficient knowledge about autism, while similar findings exist for diabetes (Boden et al., 2012; Kise, Hopkins & Burke, 2017; Gomez et al., 2020) and asthma (Berger et al., 2018; Irwin et al., 2018; Getch, Neuharth-Pritchett & Schilling, 2019), the two other diseases which have been particularly examined at a global level. Selekman (2017), in her research on the challenge of chronic conditions for teachers, points out that although the incidence of chronic conditions is increasing, teachers' knowledge about them is not.

Knowledge, however, plays an important role in the attitude of teachers towards children with special needs and in their real and meaningful inclusion in education, and as Symeonidou and Phtiaka (2014) indicate in their research in Cyprus on children with special needs, both basic and in-service training need redesign. This lack of knowledge by teachers creates strong concerns for parents about the safety and education of their children but also leads to discrimination against children with chronic diseases at school.

As the participants reveal, it is not only a question of lack of knowledge on the part of teachers and other weaknesses of the system, but there are also teachers who are not particularly interested in taking responsibility for children with chronic diseases at school. For the participants, a lot depends on educational patriotism, i.e. the personality of the teacher, his sensitivity and generally his character, with all that this implies for the children and their colleagues in the school.

Although there is certainly a portion of people who can be considered at least apathetic, nevertheless the specific question of educational patriotism should not be considered unrelated to factors beyond the individual's personality. Indeed, as reported by some participants, the attitude towards them and the discrediting of their profession sometimes determine their own attitudes and behavior, decision-making and adoption of change, with all that this implies for children with chronic diseases or other special needs at school. Therefore, although the attitude of teachers, whether positive or negative, is related to personality and other special characteristics, other external factors play their own big or small role.

For example, some teachers report that they are negatively affected and feel a strong sense of injustice, because of the negative image that the media presents of them and their profession, or because of the pressure exerted by parents and their increased or unreasonable demands. As Gidlund (2018) explains, the teacher exists within a specific space, time and context, the characteristics of which affect him each time, whether these are the attitudes of others towards them (students, parents, colleagues) or the system itself, politics, and historical context. In practice, however, negative attitudes or indifference, combined with lack of knowledge, can lead to discrimination against children with chronic diseases.

5. Limitations

Any research, however qualitative and thorough, always has areas for improvement. Despite its limitations, the research at hand takes a penetrating look at a world that is largely unknown in Cyprus and at a particularly sensitive issue, that of children with chronic diseases that are still invisible in our education system.

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